

AKADEMIA E STUDIMEVE ALBANOLOGJIKE
INSTITUTI I ANTROPOLOGJISË KULTURORE
DHE I STUDIMIT TË ARTIT

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FEDERICA POMPEJANO

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INVESTIGATING 20th CENTURY RURALITY AT DIFFERENT SCALES: THE MAMO WEBINAR CYCLE

Introduction

The webinar cycle *Materializing-Modernity: Landscape, Architecture and Anthropology Intersections in 20th Century Rurality*¹ was organized and implemented from April 12, 2021, to May 6, 2021, in order to discuss the Albanian rural landscape and its multifaceted characteristics and challenges at the international level, and to place it within the wider framework of European studies on 20th century rurality². The MaMo Webinar Cycle aimed to bring together experts in the field of architecture, ethnography, visual anthropology, cultural landscapes, and cultural heritage to discuss different methodological and interdisciplinary approaches to the study of 20th century rurality through different lenses.

¹ The MaMo Webinar Cycle has been realized and implemented, within the framework of the EU-funded project *Materializing Modernity – Socialist and Post-Socialist Rural Legacy in Contemporary Albania (MaMo)*, by Federica Pompejano (MSCA-IF Researcher), the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies (IAKSA), the Department of Cultural Heritage and Environment and the Laboratory of Ethnomusicology and Visual Anthropology (LEAV) of the University of Milan (UNIMI), Milan, Italy. All the graphic materials and webinar recordings are available in the MaMo Community webpage on Zenodo at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/materializingmodernity-mamoproject/about/> (Accessed: December 8th, 2021).

² The programme and the abstracts of the oral contributions are published at the end of this Journal.

Tackling and unfolding the theme of 20th century rurality through diverse methodological approaches, the MaMo Webinar Cycle sought to provide answers to the following questions: How can we explore, document, investigate and interpret these contexts? How can memories, cultural practices and traditions of the communities who still experience, or have experienced, these rural contexts and landscapes be investigated?

The contribution *The Albanian village as an anthropological encounter of modernity* presented by Olsi Lelaj and Nebi Bardhoshi³, discussed the space and place of the Albanian village as an encounter in which ethnographic practice, and anthropological and societal interpretation can be intertwined to provide knowledge about how modernity impacted and changed the Albanian peasants' life during the 20th century. Lelaj and Bardhoshi gave insights on the Albanian ethnographic school that started during the communist period as part of the archaeological commission in the Sector of History, Sociology and Economy of the Instituti i Shkencave, i.e., the Institute of Sciences (Bardhoshi and Lelaj 2018, 17). They pointed out how for Albanian ethnology, under communist ideology, the peasantry's life was seen as a fertile cultural territory within which to investigate and identify the national culture of the country.

From the rural village as an encounter for understanding a socio-cultural rural context, the cycle continued to the investigation and documentation of socio-cultural rural practices of a past rurality as sonic and visual marker in the ever-changing contemporary rurality. Nicola Scaldaferri and Lorenzo Ferrarini⁴, in their joint presentation *Exploring*

³ Olsi Lelaj is a researcher and a scholar of the anthropology of modernity in the Department of Ethnology at the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies (IAKSA) in Tirana. Since September 2017, he is the Head of the Department of Ethnology at IAKSA. Nebi Bardhoshi is Associate Professor and the director of the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies in Tirana (IAKSA). Since 2015, he has been a research fellow at the Graduate School for East and Southeast European Studies in Regensburg, Germany.

⁴ Nicola Scaldaferri is an ethnomusicologist and an Associate Professor at the Department of Cultural Heritage and Environment of the Università Statale di Milano (UNIMI), where he teaches Ethnomusicology and Anthropology of Music. He is the director of the *Laboratory of Ethnomusicology and Visual Anthropology*

Rurality in Southern Italy: the experience of “Sonic Ethnography” explored rurality in Southern Italy by means of sonic ethnographic methods, demonstrating how sound in the rural landscape plays an important role in determining local identities that are continuously reaffirmed by the practice of performing. Scaldaferrri and Ferrarini gave insights into their experience with Sonic Ethnography by introducing three case studies in the Basilicata region, in Italy: (1) the sonic appropriation of space by the bell carriers of San Mauro Forte; (2) the manual reaping competition in Terranova di Pollino; (3) the voices and sounds’ recordings of the home village made for the migrant communities in the United States of America. The first two case studies represent an example of sounds from a rural past that, generation after generation, continue to mark the identity of the local population. The last case study stems from the analysis of an almost lost private archive containing voices and sounds recordings that Giuseppe Chiaffitella collected as a sort of vehicle of memories for a distant Italian emigrants’ community longing for their origins. In all the presented situations, Scaldaferrri and Ferrarini demonstrated how the sound plays a crucial role in the sensory experience of a place and, recalling back past traditions and memories, can determine and re-affirm a local sense of belonging of a specific community (Ferrarini and Scaldaferrri 2020, 129).

The most continuous and most evident imprint left in the landscape over the time by humans is the texture formed by agricultural landscapes, which overlaps a large part of countries’ territories with a regular geometry of fields, rows, terraces, canals, roads, and settlements.

20th-century modernity affected many rural landscapes in Europe and the introduction of modern agricultural intensive production often followed the implementation of agrarian reforms and reclamation projects that completely changed the pre-existing landscape.

(LEAV). Lorenzo Ferrarini is a filmmaker, photographer and sound recordist based at the University of Manchester, where he teaches ethnographic documentary at the *Granada Centre for Visual Anthropology*.

Cristina Pallini and Axel Fisher⁵ introduced case studies from the EU-funded project MODSCAPES⁶, which addressed agricultural colonisation projects implemented during the 20th century, claiming that such projects, despite being conceived in different political and ideological contexts as part of a nation-building strategy, are a distinctive feature of recent European history, and provided a supra-national testing ground for experts from many disciplines.

In her contribution titled *Embedded the Past into Modernist Rural Landscapes*, Cristina Pallini shed light on two case studies: the cases of the modernist rural landscapes of Northern Greece (1920s) and the Pontine Plain in central Italy (1930s). Pallini puts emphasis on these two case studies as results of opposite governmental rural policies. In fact, the rural modernisation policies in Northern Greece were an internationally agreed response to a geo-political and humanitarian crisis in the aftermath of the Greco-Turkish war (1919-1922), while in Fascist Italy, the example of the Pontine Marshes' reclamation works, was part of Mussolini's rural policies towards national self-sufficiency.

Despite the profound differences between the two case studies, Pallini underlined how both dealt with traces from a distant past in the landscape: respectively, the *Via Appia* in Italy and the *Via Egnatia* in Greece that composed the ancient roman route from the Adriatic to the Black Sea. This research led to an interesting landscape analysis that demonstrated how those different rural policies strategically embedded these ancient traces in the new modern rural schemes. Pallini critically interpreted these modernist

⁵ Cristina Pallini is an Architect based in Milan and Associate Professor of Architectural and Urban Design at the School of Architecture Urban Planning Construction Engineering of the Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI). Axel Fisher is an architect, scholar, educator, and editor. He is Associate Professor in Belgium, at the Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), School of Architecture *La Cambre Horta*. He is involved in research activities at the *hortence lab* for architectural history, criticism, and theory.

⁶ More info about the MODSCAPES project can be found at: <https://heranet.info/projects/hera-2016-uses-of-the-past/modernist-reinventions-of-the-rural-landscapes/> (Accessed: December 13th, 2021).

rural landscapes by identifying which elements of the historical palimpsest played a role in the 20th century's modern rural schemes, challenging the notion of heritage as a potential catalyst in a latent present order liable to predict possible futures.

An introduction to the oblivion of the rural planning at the architectural and territorial levels in the former Eastern Bloc was presented by Axel Fisher in his presentation *Figures in a landscape: notes for a history of rural planning and village design in the Eastern bloc*. Fisher addressed both visual and quantitative data in order to outline major shifts and breaks in socialist countries' agricultural modernization policies within main chronological periods. The interlacing of quantitative and qualitative data in Fisher's contribution are a reminder of the need to interlace different sources in a re-evaluation of 20th-century rural planning experts and professionals that contributed to the decision-making processes that shaped the rural landscapes in the former Eastern Bloc. At the same time, he aimed at situating the modernist rural artefacts in a wider historical perspective concerning the architectural theory and practice in former socialist European countries.

Centring the focus on landscape studies during our last century, scholars agree in acknowledging that landscape is a palimpsest of tangible and intangible traces. The landscape evolves with the society that inhabits it and is the mirror of its historical and social events, economic and political problems, and of cultural contrasts and nuances. It is a legacy that we are supposed to recognize, interpret, and include in our-present-time through heritage-making processes. These processes are always selective, being articulated through time in the notions of history, memory, identity, and authenticity. They demand an interdisciplinary, critical, and integrated approach (Vigotti and Pompejano 2020). In his presentation, Bosse Lagerqvist⁷ discussed on the notion of integrated conservation as an

⁷ Bosse Lagerqvist is an Associate professor at the Department of Conservation, University of Gotehnburg (UGOT) in Sweden. Between 2012 and 2018 he has been Head of Department at the same University. He has been the leader of the EU-funded Erasmus+ Partnership on *Sustainable Management of Cultural Landscapes*, also representing the University of Gothenburg in the UNISCAPE network.

approach for heritage practices, to improve the sustainability of planning and managing landscapes, enhancing the resilience of society. Starting from defining the notion of heritage and landscape as complementary, Lagerqvist delved into the need of adopting the integrated conservation approach that considers landscape as the arena for heritage, in which natural and cultural history are interlaced. He stressed the need to examine it through a holistic perspective able to address the dynamic management of inevitable transformation processes.

Dumitru Rusu⁸ closed the MaMo webinar cycle by introducing the participants to the *Socialist Modernism* platform⁹ which is an initiative promoted by the Bureau for Art and Urban Research Association (*Birou pentru Art si Cercetare Urbană - B.A.C.U.*) based in Romania.

Rusu advocates for the protection of the socialist modernism architecture erected in Central and Eastern Europe in the period 1955-1991. The initiative he presented aims at researching, mapping, and monitoring the current state of preservation of socialist architectural elements and landscape markers. Moreover, the interactive map has been conceived as a community-driven tool with the objective of setting up and nurturing an open access database accessible to public. The community-driven mapping tool is also a way of raising the awareness among different stakeholders, underlining the importance to involve and engage the large online public in the participatory architectural heritage mapping initiatives.

What emerged from the variety of case studies presented during the webinar was the necessity to approach all of the different and multifaceted aspects of 20th-century rurality through an interdisciplinary methodology that considers qualitative and quantitative characteristics that strongly marked our most recent past. In fact, those legacies are still impacting our contemporaneity being heritage, understood in its most general meaning, as a link to the past and a door into the future. From this situation emerges

⁸ Dumitru Rusu is an architect and President of *B.A.C.U. Association - Birou pentru Art si Cercetare Urbană* (Bureau for Art and Urban Research), based in Bucharest, Romania. He is vice-president of the ICOMOS International – ISC20C.

⁹ The platform is available at <http://socialistmodernism.com/> (Accessed: December 5th, 2021).

the urgent need to deeply understand how 20th-century modernity impacted rural landscapes and their communities, and how these traces and legacies of a recent past in the present can be explored, documented, investigated, and interpreted through different methods and approaches. In Simmel's words "in the immediate sense, as in the symbolic sense, in the corporeal sense, as in the spiritual sense, it is we, at every moment, who separate what is connected and connect what is separate" (Simmel 1903, 3), just as it is we that constantly shape the *biography* of our landscapes and vice versa.

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ANNEX

THE MAMO WEBINAR CYCLE: PROGRAMME AND ABSTRACTS

The webinar cycle *Materializing-Modernity: Landscape, Architecture and Anthropology Intersections in 20th Century Rurality*¹ was organized and implemented from April 12, 2021, to May 6, 2021. It has been realized and implemented within the framework of the EU-funded project *Materializing Modernity – Socialist and Post-socialist Rural Legacy in Contemporary Albania (MaMo)*, by Federica Pompejano (MSCA-IF Researcher, Academy of Albanian Studies), the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies (IAKSA), the Department of Cultural Heritage and Environment and the Laboratory of Ethnomusicology and Visual Anthropology (LEAV) of the University of Milan (UNIMI), Milan, Italy.

The MaMo Webinar Cycle was part of a project that received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 896925.

The following pages contain the programme of the MaMo Webinar Cycle and the abstracts (in English and Albanian languages) of each oral presentation in order to give a more complete and a better understanding of the topics covered during the implementation of the webinar.

Prepared by Federica Pompejano

¹ All the graphic materials and webinar recordings are available in the MaMo Community webpage on Zenodo at:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/materializingmodernity-mamoproject/about/>.

CIKLI I UEBINAREVE MAMO: PROGRAMI DHE ABSTRAKTET

Cikli i uebinareve *Materializing-Modernity: Landscape, Architecture and Anthropology Intersections in 20th Century Rurality* u organizua dhe u realizua nga data 12 prill 2021 deri më 6 maj 2021, nga Federica Pompejano (kërkuese MSCA-IF, Instituti i Antropologjisë Kulturore dhe Studimeve të Artit - IAKSA, Akademia e Studimeve Albanologjike, Departamenti i Trashëgimisë Kulturore dhe Mjedisit dhe Labororit i Etnomuzikologjisë dhe Antropologjisë Vizuale - LEAV) të Universitetit të Milanos (UNIMI), Milano, Itali, në kuadër të projektit “Materializimi i Modernitetit – Trashëgimia Rurale Socialiste dhe Post-socialiste në Shqipërinë Bashkëkohore (MaMo)”, financuar nga Bashkimi Evropian.

Cikli i Uebinareve MaMo ishte pjesë e një projekti që mori fonde nga programi i kërkimit dhe inovacionit Horizon 2020 i Bashkimit Evropian Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action nën marrëveshjen Nr. 896925. Për të pasur një kuadër sa më të detajuar, në faqet në vijim gjendet programi i ciklit të Uebinareve MaMo dhe abstraktet (Anglisht dhe Shqip) për kumtesat e mbajtura dhe temat e trajtuara.

Përgatitur nga Federica Pompejano

Webinar
April-May 2021

Materializing Modernity

Landscape, Architecture and
Anthropology intersections
in 20th-century rurality

In many European countries, **modernity** seems to have been regarded chiefly as a state-based ideological and experimental project, providing an opportunity for new rural landscape and architectural ideas converging on the vision imposed by diverse ideologies.

In this context and regardless of the nature of the political ideology, the pre-existing *rural landscape* underwent reshaping processes that reflected into tangible transformations and interventions.

During **20th-century** and at different times, many countries demonstrated all the difficulties involved in addressing and incorporating the memories, material culture and societal evidence of those modernisation processes, and the remains they left into the new democratic present. These *tangible traces of the past* represent remembrances of unsuccessful economic policies and lost political bets, encompassing cultural, societal, anthropological, and historical values and memories, still impacting people who live in those territories. How can we **explore, document, investigate and interpret** these rural realities? This webinar wishes to bring together experts in the field of architecture, ethnography, visual anthropology, cultural landscapes and heritage and discuss different methodological and multidisciplinary approaches to the study of **modernist rurality through different lenses**.

This webinar is part of the project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 844652

LEAV....
Laboratorio di Etnoarcheologia e Archeologia Visiva
Università degli Studi di Milano

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO
DIPARTIMENTO DI BENI CULTURALI
E AMBIENTALI

IAKSA
Istituto di Archeologia e Scienze Antiche
Università degli Studi di Milano

Fig. 5 Introduction to the MaMo Webinar Cycle, F. Pompejano, 2021

MaMo **Materializing Modernity**
 Landscape, Architecture and
 Anthropology intersections
 in 20th-century rurality

Webinar Programme*

April 12, 2021|17:00-19:00 [GMT +2:00] Rome|Event code [01W]|ID MEETING: 885 7741 2108|PASSCODE: 536619

MaMo: an introduction to Albanian Socialist and Post-Socialist rurality

Federica Pompejano, MSCA-IF Fellow | Department of Ethnology, Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies, Academy of Albanian Studies, Albania

The Albanian Village as an anthropological encounter of modernity

Nebi Bardhoshi, Associate Professor | Department of Ethnology, Director of the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies, Academy of Albanian Studies, Albania

Olisi Lelaj, Researcher | Department of Ethnology, Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies, Academy of Albanian Studies, Albania

April 20, 2021|17:30-19:00 [GMT +2:00] Rome|Event code [02W]|ID MEETING: 816 5431 0504|PASSCODE: 283424

Exploring Rurality in Southern Italy: the experience of "Sonic Ethnography"

Nicola Scaldaferrì, Associate Professor | Department of Cultural and Environmental Heritage, Università Statale di Milano, Italy

Lorenzo Ferrarini, Lecturer in Social and Visual Anthropology | Granada Centre for Visual Anthropology, University of Manchester, United Kingdom

April 22, 2021|17:00-19:00 [GMT +2:00] Rome|Event code [03W]|ID MEETING: 863 9792 7066|PASSCODE: 176601

Embedding the Past into Modernist Rural Landscapes

Cristina Pallini, Associate Professor | Department of Architecture, Built Environment and Construction Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Figures in a landscape: notes for a history of rural planning and village design in the Eastern bloc

Axel Fischer, Associate Professor p.t. | Université libre de Bruxelles, School of Architecture La Cambre Horta, horticen lab for architectural history, theory and criticism, Belgium

April 29, 2021|17:00-18:30 [GMT +2:00] Rome|Event code [04W]|ID MEETING: 815 2266 8030|PASSCODE: 047217

Concepts integrated conservation as inroads to sustainable management of cultural landscapes

Bosse Lagerqvist, Associate Professor and Senior Lecturer | Department of Conservation, Göteborgs Universitet, Sweden

May 6, 2021|17:00-18:30 [GMT +2:00] Rome|Event code [05W]|ID MEETING: 832 5238 4150|PASSCODE: 323986

Socialist Modernism in the former Eastern Bloc (1955-1991)

Dumitru Rusu, President of B.A.C.U. Association- Birou pentru Art si Cercetare Urbana (Bureau for Art and Urban Research), Romania

More information?

Please, send an e-mail to federica.pompejano@asa.edu.al

Search for **@MaMoProject** on Facebook

Scan the Instagram nametag **@mamo_materializingmodernity**

* time of each event to be confirmed

HARD.MATERIALIZINGMODERNITY

This webinar is part of the project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 896625

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO
 DIPARTIMENTO DI BENI CULTURALI E AMBIENTALI

Fig. 6 The programme of the MaMo Webinar Cycle, F. Pompejano, 2021.

THE ALBANIAN VILLAGE AS AN ANTHROPOLOGICAL ENCOUNTER OF MODERNITY

Abstract

There are two ways to discuss the Albanian village as an anthropological encounter of modernity. The first encounter is when the Albanian village became the subject of ethnographic explorations and anthropological reflections. From the 20th century onward, rural life was observed as the gateway to understanding Albanian culture and society within the modern discourses of anthropology. After the foundation of the modern Albanian nation-state, the village underwent several state-oriented modernization processes that significantly changed peasants life. These “great transformations” underline the nature of the second encounter. They demand anthropological attention to understand the profound impact that modernity as a state project has had on the rural way of life in Albania. During this presentation, we will critically assess both encounters by specifically observing a) how rural life was subject to ethnological/anthropological discourses, and b) in what ways the modern state and its modernization processes have impacted the Albanian village.

FSHATI SHQIPTAR SI NJË TAKIM ANTROPOLOGJIK I MODERNITETIT

Abstrakt

Ka dy mënyra për të diskutuar fshatin shqiptar si një takim antropologjik të modernitetit. E para është kur fshati shqiptar u bë objekt i eksplorimeve etnografike dhe reflektimeve antropologjike. Në shekullin e 20-të, jeta rurale u pa si porta për të kuptuar kulturën dhe shoqërinë shqiptare brenda ligjërimeve moderne të antropologjisë. Nga ana tjetër, pas themelimit të shtetit-komb modern shqiptar, fshati iu nënshtrua disa

proceseve modernizuese të orientuara nga shteti që ndryshuan ndjeshëm jetën e fshatarëve. Këto “transformime të mëdha” nënvizojnë natyrën e dytë të takimit. Ata kërkojnë vëmendje antropologjike për të kuptuar ndikimin e thellë që moderniteti si projekt shtetëror ka pasur në mënyrën e jetesës rurale në Shqipëri. Gjatë këtij prezantimi, do t'i shqyrtojmë në mënyrë kritike të dy takimet duke vëzhguar në mënyrë specifike: a) sesi jeta rurale iu nënshtua diskurseve etnologjike/antropologjike dhe b) në çfarë mënyrash shteti modern dhe proceset e tij modernizuese kanë ndikuar në fshatin shqiptar.

Oral presenters: Nebi Bardhoshi, Associate Professor and Director of the Institute of Cultural Anthropology and Art Studies (IAKSA), Academy of Albanian Studies, and Olsi Lelaj, Researcher, Department of Ethnology, IAKSA, Academy of Albanian Studies, Albania.

Fig. 7 Images sources: Topographic map 1960s, ASIG; Kristo S. & Kodheli N., 1982, *Bujqësia ne RPSSH*, Tirana: 8 Nentori; Qerimi, V. 1964, *Lulëzo Shqipëria*, Tirana: Naim Frasher. Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

EXPLORING RURALITY IN SOUTHERN ITALY: THE EXPERIENCE OF "SONIC ETHNOGRAPHY"

Abstract

Based on research spanning thirty years, our recent book *Sonic Ethnography* reveals how sound plays a central role in the performance of local identities in the southern Italian region of Basilicata. By exploring the

soundscape of tree rituals, carnivals, pilgrimages, informal musical performances, and sound archives, the book focuses on the relational and experiential aspects of sound that momentarily bring together acoustic communities. It provides an innovative take on an area that has been studied by Italian and foreign scholars starting from the 1950s, in which these classic studies have become one of the forces at play in the local politics of heritage. In this presentation we focus on some of the sonic and visual markers of rurality - in particular carnival bells and wheat festivals - and on their current social role in people's sense of identity.

HULUMTIMI I RURALITETIT NË ITALINË JUGORE: PËRVOJA E “ETNOGRAFISË TINGULLORE”

Abstrakt

Bazuar në kërkimin që përfshin tridhjetë vjet, libri ynë i fundit *Sonic Ethnography* zbulon se si zëri luan një rol qendror në performancën e identiteteve lokale në rajonin jugor italian të Basilicata-s. Duke hulumtuar peizazhin tingullor të ritualeve të pemëve, karnavaleve, pelegrinazheve, shfaqjeve muzikore joformale dhe arkivave të tingullit, libri fokusohet në aspektet relacionale dhe eksperimentale të tingullit që bëjnë bashkë për momentin komunitete akustike. Libri ofron një qasje novatore në një fushë që është studiuar nga studiues italianë dhe të huaj duke filluar nga vitet '50-të, kontribute tanimë klasike, të cilat janë bërë një nga forcat më ta pranishme në politikën vendase të trashëgimisë. Në këtë prezantim, ne fokusohemi në disa nga shenjat tingullore dhe vizuale të fshatit - në veçanti, kambanat e karnavaleve dhe festat e grurit - dhe në rolin që këto aktualisht luajnë në identitetin e njerëzve.

Oral presenters: Nicola Scaldaferri, Associate Professor, Department of Cultural and Environmental Heritage, Università Statale di Milano, Italy;

Lorenzo Ferrarini, Lecturer in Social and Visual Anthropology, Granada Centre for Visual Anthropology, University of Manchester, United Kingdom.

Fig. 8 Ferrarini L., Scaldaferrì N., 2020. Sonic ethnography - Identity, heritage and creative research practice in Basilicata, southern Italy, Manchester: Manchester University Press. Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

EMBEDDING THE PAST INTO MODERNIST RURAL LANDSCAPES

Abstract

This lecture addresses the notion of “Uses of the Past” in the conception and implementation of modernist rural landscapes, with a focus on the case studies of Italy (Pontine Plain and Apulia) and Northern Greece. Here the Pontine Plain and Northern Greece stand out as polar opposites: one as a repository of projects, which left their mark on subsequent geographic works, the second as an (almost) neglected region stepping into modernisation out of a refugee crisis and backed by international institutions. A common denominator lies in the interplay of different levels: a territorial vision entailing vestiges of antiquity as a “latent order,” the technicalities of reclamation, and related architectural landmarks. The problem of heritage shifts in perspective. Questioning relevant precedents to discover which elements of the historical palimpsest could still play a part in a new scheme may greatly contribute to an operational understanding of the vital relationship between landscape and architecture.

PËRFSHIRJA E SË KALUARËS NË PEIZAZHET RURALE MODERNE

Abstrakt

Ky leksion trajton nocionin e “përdorimeve të së kaluarës” në konceptimin dhe realizimin e peizazheve rurale moderniste. Në fokus janë rastet studimore të Italisë (fushat Pontine dhe Pulia) dhe Greqisë Veriore. Këtu rrafshnalta e Pontinës dhe Greqia Veriore shquhen si të kundërta: njëra si një depo projektesh, që lanë gjurmët e tyre në punimet e mëvonshme gjeografike, e dyta si një rajon (pothuajse) i lënë pas dore që po shkon drejt modernizimit pas krizës së refugjatëve dhe i mbështetur nga institucione ndërkombëtare. Një emërues i përbashkët qëndron në ndërveprimin e niveleve të ndryshme: një vizion territorial që përfshin gjurmët e antikitetit si një “rend latent”, teknikat e bonifikimit dhe monumentet arkitekturore të lidhura me to. Problemi i trashëgimisë ndryshon në perspektivë. Vënia në pikëpyetje e precedentëve përkatës për të zbuluar se cilët elementë të palimpsestit historik mund të luajnë ende një rol në një skemë të re, mund të kontribuojë shumë për të kuptuar në një mënyrë më të plotë marrëdhënien jetike midis peizazhit dhe arkitekturës.

Fig. 9 Pontina, Pontine Plain, Italy. Courtesy of Pallini, Cristina. Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

Oral presenter: Cristina Pallini, Associate Professor, Department of Architecture, Built Environment and Construction Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy.

FIGURES IN A LANDSCAPE: NOTES FOR A HISTORY OF RURAL PLANNING AND VILLAGE DESIGN IN THE EASTERN BLOC

Abstract

This lecture addresses the oblivion of rural planning and village design expertise in the former Eastern bloc. To this end, the major issues at stake in this field of expertise across the short 20th-century will be singled out. “Figures” of two different natures – quantitative and visual – are discussed in parallel. On one side, official agricultural statistics concerning average surfaces and populations of state and collective farms allow the identification of major shifts and breaks in socialist countries’ agricultural modernization policies and outline major chronological eras. Against this framework, model planning schemes and architectural layouts drawn from a limited number of reference publications on socialist rural architecture and planning acquire deeper historical meaning. Over all, this contribution aims to outline a number of research questions for further inquiry, which may be of interest for a general reevaluation of 20th-century rural planning and village design expertise, but also to situate rural built heritage artefacts in a wider historical perspective.

FIGURA NË NJË PEIZAZH: SHËNIME PËR NJË HISTORI TË PLANIFIKIMIT RURAL DHE PROJEKTIMIT TË FSHATIT NË BLOKUN LINDOR

Abstrakt

Kjo ligjëratë trajton braktisjen e ekspertizës së planifikimit rural dhe projektimit të fshatit në ish-blokun lindor. Për këtë qëllim, do të veçohen çështjet kryesore që paraqiten si më të rrezikuara në këtë fushë të ekspertizës, gjatë shekullit të shkurtër të 20-të. “Figura” të dy natyrave të ndryshme – sasiore dhe vizuale – diskutohen paralelisht. Nga njëra anë, statistikat zyrtare të bujqësisë në lidhje me sipërfaqet mesatare dhe

popullsinë e fermave shtetërore dhe kolektive lejojnë identifikimin e ndryshimeve dhe ndërprerjeve të mëdha në politikat e modernizimit bujqësor të vendeve socialiste dhe përshkruajnë epokat kryesore kronologjike. Kundër këtij kuadri, skemat modele të planifikimit dhe paraqitjet arkitekturore të nxjerra nga një numër i kufizuar botimesh referuese mbi arkitekturën dhe planifikimin socialist rural fitojnë kuptim më të thellë historik. Mbi të gjitha, ky kontribut synon të përvijojë një sërë pyetjesh kërkimore për studime të mëtejshme, të cilat mund të jenë me interes për një rivlerësim të përgjithshëm të ekspertizës së planifikimit rural të shekullit të 20-të dhe projektimit të fshatit, por edhe për të vendosur artefaktet e trashëgimisë së ndërtuar rurale në një perspektivë historike më të gjerë.

Fig. 10 Collage of: [above] “Sown areas of State and Collective and Individual Farms, 1913-1932” (from: L. Kogan (ed.) *The Struggle for Five Years In Four*, Izostat Institute – State Publishing House of Fine Arts, 1932) & [below] “Grain state farm Gigant in the Rostov-on-Don oblast, panorama, 1928” (from: N.V. Baranov (ed.), *General history of architecture*, vol.12, book 1, *Architecture of the USSR*, Moscow, Stroyizdat, 1975). Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

Oral presenter: Axel Fischer, Associate Professor p.t., Université libre de Bruxelles, School of Architecture La Cambre Horta, hortence lab for architectural history, theory and criticism, Belgium.

CONCEPTS OF INTEGRATED CONSERVATION AS INROADS TO SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF CULTURAL LANDSCAPES

Abstract

The concept of integrated conservation emerges in the 1970s with the increased understanding of historical environments' importance as resources in urban and land-use planning, which cannot be delimited as a secondary issue in societal development. Sir Bernard Feilden defined the concept in 1986 as the dynamic management of change in order to reduce the rate of decay. Apart from more or less nature-given external and internal causes of decay, the most troublesome are manmade causes such as fashion, wars, pollution, and not the least – stupidity. These factors drive landscape change, but other factors are also important: for example technology development, market dynamics, urbanisation, 'silo planning', or policy interventions. Integrated conservation relates to notions of heritage and the lecture will discuss heritage research and operative practices and the relation between top-down and bottom-up processes. One question that is raised regards whether it is possible to define a governance structure providing stewardship to operate managerial routines.

KONCEPTET E RUAJTJES SË INTEGRUAR SI RRUGË DREJT MENAXHIMIT TË QËNDRUESHËM TË PEIZAZHEVE KULTURORE

Abstrakt

Koncepti i ruajtjes së integruar qëndron në rritjen e ndërgjegjësimit, në vitet '70-të të rëndësisë së mjediseve historike si burime në planifikimin urban dhe në përdorimin e tokës, çka nuk mund të kufizohet si një çështje dytësore në zhvillimin shoqëror. Sir Bernard Feilden e përcaktoi konceptin në 1986 si menaxhim dinamik i ndryshimit në mënyrë që të reduktojë shkallën e degradimit. Përveç shkaqeve pak a shumë të jashtme dhe të brendshme të degradimit nga natyra, ato më shqetësueset janë shkaqet e

krijuara nga njeriu si: moda, luftërat, ndotja dhe po ashtu, marrëzia njerëzore. Këta faktorë nxisin ndryshimin e peizazhit, por i rëndësishëm është gjithashtu, për shembull, zhvillimi i teknologjisë, dinamika e tregut, urbanizimi, “planifikimi i siloseve” ose ndërhyrjet e politikave të ndryshme. Ruajtja e integruar lidhet me nocionet mbi trashëgiminë dhe ligjërata do të diskutojë rreth kërkimeve mbi trashëgiminë, praktikat operative dhe lidhjen ndërmjet proceseve nga lart-poshtë dhe nga poshtë-lart. Një çështje e hapur është nëse mund të përcaktohet një strukturë qeverisëse që siguron administrimin e një rutine menaxheriale.

Fig. 11 Former open lignite pit, Saxony, Germany. Photo courtesy of Bosse Lagerqvist. Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

Oral presenter: Bosse Lagerqvist, Associate Professor and Senior Lecturer, Department of Conservation, Göteborgs Universitet, Sweden.

SOCIALIST MODERNISM IN THE FORMER EASTERN BLOC (1955-
1991) THE SOCIALIST MODERNISM MAP:
SOCIALISTMODERNISM.COM

Abstract

Socialist architecture and more precisely the modernist tendencies of the 1955-1991 period, as a concept, are becoming more and more popular in specialists' circles. In our case, “Socialist Modernism” is a research

platform created by the B.A.C.U. Association. It focuses on modernist trends from Central and Eastern Europe that are insufficiently explored in the broader context of global architecture. Modernism in architecture first arose in Western European capitalist societies, following a series of essential principles such as “form follows function”, the use of mass-produced materials, the adoption of industrial aesthetics, simplicity and formal clarity, and the elimination of unnecessary details, etc. In post-war Eastern European socialist countries, on the other hand, modernist trends first influenced the professional sphere, and through that influence, they were able to penetrate borders and the limits imposed by the Socialist ideology. In Central and Eastern Europe there are several important architectural monuments, representative of the post-WWII identity of each country and expressing the aspirations of socialist architects. Examples include the “Romanita” Collective Housing Building-Chisinau, the Buzludzha Memorial - Bulgaria, the Emilia Pavilion – Warsaw, etc. The objective of the project is an interactive map that would display the most valuable examples of Socialist Modernist architecture from 1955 to 1991. The interactive map is a community-driven tool focused on increasing our database, as well as promoting awareness to preserve these buildings. Anyone who is passionate about this historical period can join our cause by supporting it on Instagram, Tumblr, Twitter, and Pinterest, by posting with the #socialistmodernism hashtag. All important socialist modernist landmarks will be included on this platform, so they can be easily accessed by anyone interested in such vestiges.

MODERNIZMI SOCIALIST NË ISH-BLLOKUN LINDOR (1955-1991)

HARTA E MODERNIZMIT SOCIALIST:

SOCIALISTMODERNISM.COM

Abstrakt

Arkitektura socialiste dhe, më saktësiht, prirjet moderniste të periudhës 1955-1991, si koncept, po bëhen gjithnjë e më të njohura në rrethet e

specialistëve. Në rastin tonë, “Modernizmi Socialist” është një platformë kërkimore e krijuar nga Shoqata B.A.C.U, e cila fokusohet në tendencat moderniste të shfaqura në Evropën qendrore dhe lindore dhe që, përgjithësisht, janë eksploruar në mënyrë të pamjaftueshme në kontekstin më të gjerë të arkitekturës globale. Modernizmi në arkitekturë u ngrit fillimisht në shoqëritë kapitaliste të Evropës perëndimore, duke ndjekur një sërë parimesh thelbësore si: “forma ndjek funksionin”, përdorimi i materialeve të prodhuara në masë, adoptimi i estetikës industriale, thjeshtësia dhe qartësia e formës dhe eliminimi i detajeve të panevojshme. Në vendet socialiste të Evropës lindore të pasluftës, tendencat moderniste ndikuan fillimisht sferën profesionale dhe, nëpërmjet këtij ndikimi, mundën të depërtonin në kufijtë dhe limitet e vendosur nga ideologjia socialiste. Në Evropën Qendrore dhe Lindore ka disa monumente të rëndësishme arkitekturore, përfaqësuese të identitetit të çdo vendi të pas Luftës së Dytë Botërore dhe shprehin aspiratat e arkitektëve socialistë. Shembujt përfshijnë: Ndërtesën e Banesave Kolektive “Romanita”- Kisinau, Memorialin Buzludzha – Bullgari; Pavijonin Emilia – Varshavë, etj. Objektiv i projektit është një hartë interaktive që do të shfaqë shembujt më të vlefshëm të arkitekturës socialiste moderniste nga 1955 deri në 1991. Harta interaktive është një mjet i drejtuar nga komuniteti i fokusuar në rritjen e bazës së të dhënave tona, si dhe në promovimin e ndërgjegjësimit për ruajtjen e këtyre ndërtesave. Kushdo që është i interesuar pas kësaj periudhe historike mund t’i bashkohet kauzës sonë duke e mbështetur atë në Instagram, Tumblr, Twitter dhe Pinterest, duke postuar me hashtagun *#socialistmodernism*. Në këtë platformë do të përfshihen monumente të rëndësishme moderniste socialiste, në mënyrë që të mund të konsultohen lehtësisht nga kushdo që është i interesuar për gjurmë të tilla.

Fig. 12 Photo: B.A.C.U. Association, www.socialistmodernism.com. Graphic processing: F. Pompejano, 2021.

Përmbajtja

- MATERIALIZING-MODERNITY: LANDSCAPE, ARCHITECTURE,
AND ANTHROPOLOGY INTERSECTIONS IN 20TH-CENTURY RURALITY
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Investigating 20th-Century Rurality at Different Scales: The MaMo Webinar Cycle
- 2. OLSI LELAJ, NEBI BARDHOSHI
The Albanian Village and Modernity: An Outline of a Relation
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